

Enabling Gem5 Full System Simulation for Modern Android

1 Motivation

Modern mobile workloads rely heavily on multi-threading and graphics processing. Single threaded user-level simulation is not sufficient to faithfully model their behavior. Historically, Gem5 has supported Full-System simulation for the Android OS, releasing official guides up to Marshmallow and Nougat. However, over the past decade, this infrastructure has become obsolete, both due to changes in the Gem5 simulator and in the modern Android OS, whose architecture has changed significantly, especially from version 11 onwards. For these reasons, running modern Android in Gem5 requires a non-trivial effort. In this work, we describe the major changes to both the simulator and the OS required for running Android 14 in Gem5 version 25.0. Moreover, we argue that realistic architectural simulation for today’s mobile SoCs cannot rely on CPU-based rendering. However, a precise GPU architectural model drastically increases the already substantial simulation time required to boot the system and execute realistic workloads. To overcome this limitation, we propose a VirtIO GPU device for Gem5, capable of offloading rendering to the host GPU, balancing simulation time and realism for CPU-focused architectural research.

2 System Configuration

Experimental Setup	
Gem5 Base	v25.0
Android Base	Ver. 14 release 01
Kernel Base	Linux Android14-6.1
Guest Architecture	arm64-v8a
Platform	VExpress_GEM5_V1

To successfully boot Android 14, several compatible components are required: Linux kernel, device tree, several devices and appropriately configured OS images. Table 2 summarizes the baseline components we used in this setup. We integrated the Linux kernel for Android version 6.1 with Gem5-specific .config files available for Linux 5.15.36 and a custom DTB that aligns with OS and kernel expectations. Moreover, we developed a simulator-friendly Android build, taking from the existing Goldfish and Cuttlefish builds and removing the

components specifically designed for Android Emulator and Qemu. In Gem5, we based our configuration on the VExpress.GEM5_V1 Realview platform, adding several IDE Controllers for the disk images, a VirtIO RNG device for random number generation and a PL111 device as display.

3 Offloading GPU Rendering

Figure 1: Graphics stack and device model for the VirtIO GPU device.

Building on the setup described in Section 2, we developed a VirtIO-based passthrough GPU device to perform graphics rendering for the simulated workloads directly on the host GPU. We rely on the Mesa 3D graphics library, which supports VirtIO devices, and the GPU DRM driver modules introduced in Linux 6.1. We model our GPU according to the VirtIO specification. VirtIO GPU devices require support for the non-legacy VirtIO protocol (1.0+). However, the VirtIO device support in Gem5 is limited to legacy devices. We developed a ModernVirtIODevice class and a PciVirtIOModern wrapper class to allow using modern VirtIO devices over PCI. The VirtIO GPU specification supports a variety of optional features. Among these, we added support for the features required to integrate with the Android graphics stack, namely context initialization, EDID, and Virgl options. Since Gem5, differently from Qemu, does not support host-visible memory, we do not support resource blob and host visible memory options. For the same reason, our device model relies on explicit copies of resources between guest and host memory for graphics rendering. To avoid artificially increasing memory traffic for the simulated system, the resource copies required to keep host-side and guest-side resources coherent are performed in functional mode, which does not impact simulation behavior.